

RESIDUAL TENSILE PROPERTIES OF GFRP PIPES AGED UNDER HIGH PRESSURE AND TEMPERATURE CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper evaluates the tensile properties in the axial direction of GFRP pipes aged under high pressure (73 and 89 bar) and high temperatures (60°C and 93°C) through time. The tests were performed according to ASTM D3039-17. The modulus of elasticity showed the highest degradation compared to the condition without aging. The aging affected the tensile modulus of elasticity much more significantly than the tensile strength. The aging conditions at 89 bar were the most aggressive, generating macroscopic delaminations and the greatest losses in tensile properties.

KEYWORDS

Aging; high pressure; high temperature; residual modulus of elasticity; residual tensile strength

INTRODUCTION

Fiberglass-reinforced polymer matrix (GFRP) composite pipes have been produced for supplying transportation services of fluids such as natural gas, water, corrosive liquids, and oil (Gunoz et al., 2020). Among the advantages, CFRP composites show high values of their specific strength and stiffness, as well as good fatigue and corrosion resistance. In civil and industrial infrastructure, the installation, transportation, repair, and connection of GFRP pipes are more simple than traditional steel pipes (Manoj Prabhakar et al., 2019).

The composite pipes can have their properties degraded by several factors like the natural aging of the composite material, the service conditions (static or cyclic internal pressure or external loads, temperature, moisture), and the conveyed fluid. Properties such as the modulus of elasticity and tensile strength can change by the degradation of the material and, so, affect the structural integrity of the pipes (Ellyin & Maser, 2004).

Burst tests are one of the experimental tools used to analyze the structural integrity of pipes in situations close to service conditions or accelerated aging conditions to extrapolate their results to service conditions (Manoj Prabhakar et al., 2019). The test has some limitations, such as the dimensions of the specimens, the equipment necessary to simulate service conditions or accelerated aging, and costs associated with the experimental program. Reis et al. (Reis et al., 2017) proposed a model to estimate the failure pressure of thin-walled GFRP pipes using a reduced number of tensile tests. The tensile specimens were fabricated after the pipe burst test. The pipes were subjected to an internal pressure of 1 MPa (10 bar) and a temperature of 80°C for 2, 4, and 6 months. This referenced study shades light to a tool that helps the design and analysis of this type of pipe. However, other studies are still necessary to consolidate this methodology. For example, studies that allow understanding behavior of tensile properties with long aging time since different degradation processes can affect thermo-physical, mechanical, and chemical characteristics.

This paper aims to evaluate the tensile properties in the axial direction of GFRP pipes that were artificially aged under high pressure (73 and 89 bar) and high temperatures (60°C and 93°C) for planned

times of 1440 h (2 months), 4320 h (6 months), and 12960 h (18 months), although, experimentally, some of the aging periods showed to be different due to the pipes failure. The data were treated statistically to detect significant differences in the results.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Glass fiber-reinforced epoxy resin pipes were employed from two different manufacturers: A and B. Table 1 presents the technical specifications.

Table 1: Technical specifications of the pipes.

Material	Epoxy + E-type Glass fiber
Nominal diameter	200 mm (8")
Nominal internal diameter	208.8 mm (8.2")
Nominal thickness	5.5 mm (0.2")
Maximum service temperature	93°C
Maximum pressure rating	17.2 bar (249.5 psi)
HDB (93°C)	121 N/mm ²

The pipes were produced by Reciprocal Filament Wound and the fiber angle was $\pm 55^\circ$. The glass transition temperature (T_g) obtained by DMTA was 163°C and 177°C for manufactures A and B, respectively. Eight pipes of 1.0 m length were used for this research: six aged and two without aging. Table 2 presents the conditions applied to the six pipes aged using the internal hydrostatic pressure of tap water. The pressure conditions were selected according to the adjustment of the HDB (hydrostatic design basis) curve provided by the manufacturer obtained by the failure pressure recorded in the short-term hydrostatic test. The temperature of 60°C was chosen because it is the maximum operating temperature of the pipes in the field. The temperature of 93°C was used by the manufacturer to characterize the pressure class of the pipes (HDB). The experimental program followed the recommendations of the work of Reis et al. Table 2 also brings the actual aging time until each pipe failed or that had its aging process stopped; this was the case for CP3 that had its aging interrupted to produce a replica of CP4.

Table 2: Aging test conditions of the pipes.

Manufacturer	Pipe	Aging time [hours]	Pressure [bar]	Temperature [°C]
A	CP3	3360	73	60
	CP4	3360	73	60
	CP5	5040	73	93
	CP12	No aging		
B	CP9	2256	73	93
	CP10	384	89	93
	CP11	1512	89	60
	CP13	No aging		

Three specimens were obtained from each pipe. The pipes were cut transversely to their axis using a 400 mm horizontal band saw cutter, Franho brand, model FM 1600, with hydraulic advance (see Figure 1a)). Subsequently, a section parallel to the tube axis was cut as shown in Figure 1b). A Cortag disc cutter, model Zapp-200 G2, was used to obtain specimens with nominal dimensions were 15 mm width, 250 mm length and the thickness was the same as the pipe.

a) cut transversal to axis.

b) cut parallel to the axis.

Figure 1: cuts performed in the pipes to obtain the tensile specimens.

The position of each specimen in the tube is schematized in Figure 2a). The nomenclature used follows the sequence: (pipe)-(position along the pipe)-T. An example of the nomenclature of a tensile specimen obtained from the upper side of the CP_ is shown in Figure 2b).

a) Schematization of sample positions in each pipe.

b) Nomenclature.

Figure 2- Identification of the regions of the pipe and nomenclature used for each tensile test.

The tests were performed according to ASTM D3039/D3039M-17 (ASTM, 2017) using a constant head displacement rate of 2.0 mm/min. The equipment used for the tests was a Landmark 370.10 MTS servo-hydraulic drive machine, with a capacity of 100 kN and a load cell of 25 kN. Strains were measured with an axial extensometer MTS 634.12F-25 (see Figure 3). The test environment was controlled at 23 ± 2 °C and relative humidity of 50 ± 5 %. The tensile chord modulus of elasticity (E^{chord}) was calculated using a strain started point of 0.1% and a range (difference between the two strain points) of 0.2%, as recommended in the standard.

Figure 3: Specimen between the grips during a tensile test.

The results were analyzed through a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), which uses a one-dimensional analysis of variance to compare means or medians of 3 or more data groups, using a significance level of 95% (p-value = 0.05) and a Student's t-test for comparison between 2 samples with a significance level of 95%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sample mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation of the tensile chord modulus of elasticity (E^{chord}) and the ultimate tensile strength (F^{uts}) of the specimens tested from the seven pipes are presented in Table 3. Results of the E^{chord} vs. aging time and F^{uts} vs. aging time are plotted in Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively. Results of non-aging GFR epoxy $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound pipes reported by (Betts et al., 2019) from tests performed in the direction of the pipe axis are similar to the results showed in the tables.

Table 3: Sample mean, standard deviation (SD), and coefficient of variation (CV) of the tensile chord modulus of elasticity (E^{chord}) and the tensile strength (F^{uts}) for the tensile specimens from the pipes.

Pipe	Tensile chord modulus of elasticity (E^{chord})			Tensile strength (F^{uts})		
	Mean [GPa]	SD [GPa]	CV [%]	Mean [MPa]	SD [GPa]	CV [%]
CP3	9.6	0.8	8.0	56.8	2.1	3.7
CP4	10.6	0.9	8.9	44.6	0.6	1.3
CP5	6.9	0.8	12.0	40.0	4.0	10.1
CP12	13.7	0.4	2.8	55.0	3.8	6.8
CP9	5.8	0.5	9.3	41.5	2.6	6.3
CP10	6.6	1.5	22.1	40.3	4.0	9.8
CP11	6.0	0.5	8.2	39.5	8.5	21.5
CP13	8.6	0.7	8.7	48.4	0.5	11.1

Figure 4: Graph tensile chord modulus of elasticity (E^{chord}) vs. aging time for the tested conditions. Circles correspond to specimens of manufacturer A and squares to manufacturer B. The aging at 60°C and 93°C were colored in blue and red, respectively; green was used for no aged specimens. The error bars correspond to \pm standard deviation.

Figure 5: Graph tensile strength (F^{uts}) vs. aging time for the tested conditions. Circles correspond to specimens of manufacturer A and squares to manufacturer B. The aging at 60°C and 93°C were colored in blue and red, respectively; green was used for no aged specimens. The error bars correspond to \pm standard deviation.

The results at 73 bar and 3360 h show that the mean value of E^{chord} presented a decrease of 26% (on average) for the case of aging at 60°C (CP3 and 4) and 53% (also on average) for 93°C (CP5 and 9), compared with CP12 that suffered no aging. Analyzing the evolution of this parameter (temperature) at 384h, 2256h, and 3360h the correspondent CP pairs (CP's 3 and 4; CP5 and 9) statistical analysis did show a significant difference in the mean values for both temperatures. In fact, it became obvious that by increasing the temperature and keeping the pressure of 73 bar fixed, the specimen's life decreased, as can be concluded by analyzing CP9's behavior. Table 4 brings a comparison between the values of E^{chord} 's variations. The degradation of E^{chord} may be associated with the plasticization of the matrix (Rodríguez et al., 2013). The E^{chord} increase phenomena, previously reported for aging in seawater (Chakraverty et al., 2015), could not be seen in this study.

Table 4: Comparison of the tensile chord modulus of elasticity (E^{chord}) by test variable, manufacturer, and aging period.

	Manufacturer	Test Temperature	Test Pressure	Aging until failure (hours)	E^{chord} (GPa)	E^{chord} decrease (compared to no aging – same manufacturer)
CP12	A	-	-	-	13.7	-
CP3	A	73 bar	60°C	3360	9.6	30.34%
CP4	A			3360	10.6	22.74%
CP5	A		93°C	5040	6.9	49.62%
CP9	B			2256	5.8	57.47%
CP13	B	-	-	-	8.6	-
CP11	B	89 bar	60°C	1512	6.0	30.58%
CP10	B		93°C	384	6.6	23.13%

The difference between the means for the case of 89 bar with an aging time of 384 h was 52% for 93°C and 56 % for aging time of 1512 hours and 60°C. The significant decrease of E^{chord} under these

conditions, as well as the presence of defects saw in the material during the manufacture of the specimens (see Figure 6), show that it is an aggressive aging condition.

Figure 6: Example of a delamination at one end of a sample manufactured from a pipe aged at 89 bar.

The F^{uts} values after 3360 hours for the aging condition at 73 bar and 60°C showed a slight decrease of 8% (in average) compared with the non-aging coupon, but not enough to be statistically significant. A different behavior was seen in the tests at 93°C at 73 bar. A more significant difference in ultimate tensile strength drops, 14.28%, occurred between CP13 without aging and CP9 after a period of 2256 h. Table 5 brings a comparison between the values of F^{uts} 's variations. CP5, which was aged at the same test conditions as CP9, presented a drop of 27% F^{uts} final value but resisted 5040 hours of testing. This phenomenon could be explained by the fact that the pipes were produced by 2 different manufacturers. Aging at 89 bar produced a decrease in mean F^{uts} of 16.7% and 18.3% for 93°C and 60°C, respectively. No significant difference was seen between the mean F^{uts} values for the two tests temperatures at 89 bar, compared to non-aging condition (CP13). What it could be seen was that when aged at the highest temperature (93°C) while the pressure was kept at the same value (89 bar), the pipe's life was decreased. It is important to bring to attention that the 2 coupons that were degraded at the same conditions (93°C/73 bar), showed equivalent F^{uts} values after the tests but different times to failure: one after 2256 hours and the other after 5040 hours. The decrease relative to no aging specimens was 14.3% for CP9 and 27.3% for CP5 showing that the pipes of manufacturer A had the highest decrease of the residual ultimate tensile strength but more the double of life to failure.

Table 5: Comparison of the tensile strength (F^{uts}) by test variable, manufacturer, and aging period.

	Manufacturer	Test Temperature	Test Pressure	Aging until failure (hours)	F^{uts} [MPa]	E^{chord} decrease (compared to no aging – same manufacturer)
CP12	A	-	-	-	55.0	-
CP3	A	73 bar	60°C	3360	56.8	-3.27%
CP4	A			3360	44.6	18.90%
CP5	A		93°C	5040	40.0	27.23%
CP9	B			2256	41.5	14.28%
CP13	B	-	-	-	48.4	-
CP11	B	89 bar	60°C	1512	39.5	18.32%
CP10	B		93°C	384	40.3	16.74%

Reis et al. (Reis et al., 2017) evaluated the F^{uts} and the E^{chord} of pipes aged with an internal pressure of 1 MPa (10 bar) and a temperature of 80°C for 2, 4, and 6 months. The authors concluded that aging

affected the strength much more significantly than the elastic properties. The results of the present work, performed with pressures 7.3 and 8.9 times higher than those of the authors, showed an opposite trend, with the modulus of elasticity showing the highest percentage variation of degradation compared to the condition without aging.

D'Almeida et al. (d'Almeida et al., 2008) study the effect of water absorption in tensile properties of GFRP pipes. The experimental program employed ring tests and axial specimens like the used in this paper. The results showed that the water absorption significantly reduced the stiffness of the pipes, both in axial and circumferential directions. The tensile strength was not affected during the time of exposure to water. The authors attributed the degradation of the stiffness to the plasticization of the resin consequence of the water absorption. The temperatures used for aging in this paper are below the T_g of both pipes. However, the plasticization can reduce the T_g of the material (Perreux & Suri, 1997). The moisture absorption mechanism is favored by the high temperatures and pressures used in the aging process (Gautier et al., 1999) (Li et al., 2018). An additional study is necessary to evaluate how the T_g varied with the different aging cycles and if this parameter affected the modulus of elasticity.

CONCLUSIONS

Results of modulus of elasticity and ultimate tensile strength were obtained from specimens manufactured from GFRP aged under high pressure (73 and 89 bar) and high temperatures (60°C and 93°C) through time. The aging affected the tensile modulus of elasticity much more significantly than the tensile strength. The aging conditions at 89 bar were the most aggressive, generating macroscopic delaminations and the greatest losses in tensile properties..

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors would like to acknowledge the sponsorship of PETROBRAS, the Brazilian research agencies CNPq (Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico). This study was financed in part by the Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior – Brasil (CAPES) – Finance Code 001.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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